

PRE AND POST COVID COMPARATIVE STOCK MARKET STUDY USING NEURAL NETWORK AND RANDOM FOREST

¹AYUSH AWASTHI, ²TANIMA THAKUR

¹School of Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India

²Assistant Professor, School of Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India
E-mail: ¹ayushawasthih@gmail.com

Abstract - Stocks are possibly the most popular Capital instrument invented for making wealth. From last few decades we have seen an enormous increase in the volume of stock daily traded. In stock market it is very important that you have very accurate information. With the development of computer science, machine learning is now more vastly used in Stock market. The main purpose of this paper is to find the effect of COVID on prediction of daily volume of stock traded. In this paper we have used two different machine learning models: Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Random Forest (RF). The main task is to predict the volume traded for 90 days using learnings from the historical data. The dataset consists of the RELIANCE, TATA and SBIN taken from Yahoo Finance. The models are evaluated using standard strategic indicators: RMSE and MAE. It has been observed that the accuracy of Random Forest is greater than ANN in both pre and post COVID times.

Keywords - Stock Market Analysis, Machine Learning, Artificial Neural Network, Random Forest, Pre Covid Analysis, Post Covid Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Stock is a share in the ownership of a company, Stock represents a hold on the company's assets and earnings. Predicting the volume of the traded stock is a difficult task as it depends on various factors including like political stability, global economy and company's Revenue and performance etc. The COVID pandemic has affected the world economy seriously. Due to lockdown and other restriction financial market has suffered miserably [1]. It has created a high risk, making investors to bear huge losses. Stock signifies the ownership in the firm and have the claims on the profit of the company. As stock trade has high risk so knowing the predictions for the trade volume of stocks helps the investors and company to avoid losses and maximize profits. There are mainly two types of analysis in financial market: Fundamental Analysis – In this analysis we predict the value by examining the underlying factors that affect the company's business. Technical Analysis – In this analysis we look at the movement of stock and uses that data to predict the future value.

In this paper we are going to do technical analysis as the data in stock market analysis is large and non-linear. As concluded by Fama [2], financial time series prediction can be very difficult task due to the semi-strong form of efficiency and high level of noise. We need something that can find hidden trends and connection between the values. Machine learning methods in this financial area have proved to improve efficiencies by 60-86 % as compared to the past methods [3]. In research it was found that ANN has better accuracy in short term prediction [4] and in another research FEB (Feature Engineering and bootstrapping) model that is made from that is made from Random forest, Gradient boosting and bagging

have performed quite well in stock trend predictions in pre-Covid and post-Covid times [5]. Mei et al. used Random Forest for accurately Predicting real time prices of electricity market in New York [6]. Same work is done by Yand et al. they used the Random Forest to predicts the short term load on electric power systems [7]. So, we are using ANN and another RF to make analysis on pre and post covid data. Although forecasting stock through technical analysis is good in short run but for long run fundamental analysis is a suitable method. In Chinese stock market it is seen stock price can be predicted to some extent through technical analysis [8]. We are only focusing on the technical analysis in this paper of the pre and post COVID period.

II. METHODOLOGY

Description of data

The data for the three companies has been collected from yahoo finance. The dataset includes 3 years and 5 months data of Reliance, Tata motors and SBI. The data is from 04/06/2018 to 18/11/2021. We are using this range of data because we want to divide equal no of data for both Pre and Post COVID time so there is no partiality in data in either case. The dataset have information on stocks such as High, Low, Open, Close, Volume and Adjacent close.

Stock name	Pre Covid Train	Pre Covid Test	Post Covid Train	Post Covid Test
RELIANCE, TATAMOTO RS, SBIN	04/06/2018-22/10/2019	23/10/2019-28/02/2020	02/03/2020-08/07/2021	09/07/2021-18/11/2021

Table 1. Dataset Description

Normalization

The data obtained from the yahoo finance has been split and normalized. Data normalization means adjusting values measured on different scales to common scale

$$X' = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}}$$

where X = Actual input, X'= Normalized output
 X_{min} = Minimum value of data
 X_{max} = Maximum value of data

Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

ANN is a computational structure which works the same way as the biological neurons work in living being brain. In biological neural network, each neuron end relates to other neuron head, when the neuron excites it send chemical signals to the connected neurons. If the chemical signal is greater than the threshold of the neuron then it will send the chemical signal to the next neurons. It finds the underlying trend from the data given and generalizes it for other sets of data. We are using a very simple three-layer neural network i.e. An Artificial neural network with 1 hidden layer in it.

Fig.1 Neural network for Reliance Post COVID data using 1 Hidden layer.

Neural network direction flow is from left to right. In the fig.1 we can see a neural network which have five features (RELIANCE.NS.Open, RELIANCE.NS.High, RELIANCE.NS.Low, RELIANCE.NS.Close, RELIANCE.NS.Adjusted) that arrive at the input layer. The data from these five input nodes are then multiplied with set of weight which will be optimized as the algorithm runs. After the multiplication is done an Activation function is applied to the data. These numbers that we get after activation function becomes our hidden layer. In this paper 5 nodes are there in hidden layer. These set of

neurons are again multiplied with set of weight and again an Activation function is applied to the result after the multiplication. At the end we get a single data which will be our prediction value for the traded volume of stock.

Random forest

Random forest is a machine learning algorithm that uses ensemble technique (It is a technique to combine many classifier so it can find solution to a complex problem) and it is used to solve regression and classification problems. It combines many decision tree to find the final output instead of relying on single decision tree as it reduces the variance in the model. Random forest predicts the outcome by taking the mean of all the output from the different decision tree. The model we use in this paper has 12 no. of trees for all the stocks data so it doesn't create a difference when we do the comparative analysis. Random forest reduces the overfitting of data and also increases the accuracy of the output. As the noise in the stock market data is very high it makes the decision tree to grow in very unexpected way. Random forest tries to minimize the prediction error by treating the data as a classification problem and using training variable from the train dataset predicts the stock traded volume for the upcoming days. [9]

III. RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of the model we made comparison on Artificial Neural Network and Random Forest on three different companies stock Reliance, Tata Motors and SBI. We are using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) to find the final error. We are also finding the accuracy in the traded stock volume. Accuracy is computed using equation 1:

$$\text{Deviation} = (\text{Actual}-\text{Predicted})/\text{Actual}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = 1 - \text{Absolute}(\text{Mean}(\text{deviation})) \tag{1}$$

RMSE is computed using Equation 2:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\text{Predicted}_i - \text{Actual}_i)^2}{N}}$$

(2)

where N = Total no. of observation, $Predicted_i$ = Predicted value of i^{th} observation and $Actual_i$ = Actual value for the i^{th} observation.

MAE is computed using equation 3:

$$MAE = (1/n) * \sum |y_i - x_i| \quad (3)$$

N = Total no of observation, X_i = Predicted value of i^{th} observation and Y_i = Actual value for the i^{th} observation.

Fig.1 shows graph for Actual and predicted daily volume traded for Pre and Post COVID using ANN.

Fig.2 shows graph for Actual and Predicted daily volume traded for pre and post COVID using RF.

In Table 2, we have done all the analysis based on Accuracy, RMSE and MAE that we get from ANN and RF model. It can be observed that generally post Covid time has low RMSE and MAE value and accuracy is bad for Tata motors and SBI in post COVID times.

Tata Stock Trade Volume Post Covid using ANN

SBI Stock Trade Volume Pre Covid using ANN

SBI Stock Trade Volume Post Covid using ANN

Reliance Stock Trade Volume Pre Covid Using ANN

Reliance Stock Trade Volume Post Covid using ANN

Tata Stock Trade Volume Pre Covid using ANN

Fig. 1. Actual v/s predicted Daily Volume traded for 90 days using ANN

Reliance Stock Trade Volume Pre Covid using RF

Reliance Stock Trade Volume Post Covid using RF

Fig. 2. Actual v/s Predicted Daily Volume Traded for 90 days using Random Forest

Stock Name and Time Period	Artificial Neural Network (ANN)			Random Forest (RF)		
	Accuracy	RMSE	MAE	Accuracy	RMSE	MAE
Reliance pre COVID	0.5160011	0.252204	0.2007301	0.5250549	0.2645173	0.2098131
Reliance post COVID	0.8640098	0.1274311	0.0934623	0.8656665	0.2140163	0.1599509
Tata pre COVID	0.8890211	0.1304365	0.08664126	0.6146172	0.1514063	0.1079168
Tata post COVID	0.06810477	0.1404093	0.1181085	0.2984265	0.1473937	0.1051574
SBI pre COVID	0.07905506	0.2681359	0.2174894	0.8130083	0.1430001	0.09373565
SBI post COVID	-0.2553338	0.1630403	0.1295098	-3.263467	0.2216074	0.1839524

Table 2. Comparative analysis of Accuracy, RMSE and MAE values from ANN and RF model

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Stock market is very volatile and gets updated consistently. Predicting the traded volume in stock market is a complex problem and from the limited data of the post COVID time and the dataset from the yahoo finance only contains few features. Our main goal is to analyse how COVID has affected Indian

stock market and how accurately we can predict future trade volume using ANN and RF. This will be helpful for investors and companies to see the changes in the results these models have faced in Pre and Post Covid times. The comparative analysis based on RMSE and MAE we can see that generally post COVID times have low RMSE and MAE value then pre-COVID times except in SBI Post-COVID using

RF and Tata Post-COVID using ANN. Results shows that the Accuracy for Reliance stock is greater in post-COVID times while the accuracy is low for Tata and SBI in post covid times. Due to COVID accuracy has gone low for Tata and SBI stock. For future work, as more time passes, we will have more data that is of after the covid time. Having more data will significantly increase the efficiency of both algorithms. Moreover, we can also combine sentimental analysis technique with our model. There is also high potential if we made more comprehensive model which is trained on news and text based data , as news have a huge impact in the COVID times.

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